

HIGH INTEGRATION OF RESEARCH MONOGRAPHS IN THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE INFRASTRUCTURE

Deliverable D6.4: Deployable dashboard service as Open Source software (licence to be agreed) including data aggregation, display

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Project's coordinator Organization	: CLEO-CNRS
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WP and tasks contributing	: WP6 Metrics T6.6
WP leader	: UBIQUITY PRESS
Dissemination level	: PU
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Background

As part of Hirmeos WP6 about metrics, Knowledge Unlatched Research provided a dashboard built for partners to visualise and interrogate usage data from a variety of sources. The dashboard is capable of displaying usage by country and other IP range selections for each book or identifier as appropriate.

The work provides: Demonstration Shiny dashboard based on existing data, data aggregation to a functioning dashboard from the Reader Analytics Service API or directly from outputs of Statistics Collection Agent as agreed by HIRMEOS partners (M26) with a hard dependency on T6.4).

Work carried out

Using example data from Open Book Publishers and the test API provided by Ubiquity Press a dashboard application was built in Shiny, a platform that uses the R language to display data on a web platform. The dashboard was successfully deployed locally (using R Studio) and remotely on the ShinyIO platform to enable public access.

Following discussion and acceptance testing with the HIRMEOS community changes were made to the interface design to emphasise the separate metrics being obtained. To demonstrate altmetric data on a larger scale the corpus of OA books from Open Book Publishers was used to obtain data from Crossref Event Data to generate a larger dataset.

The code provided to the HIRMEOS Github organisation contains instructions for running as a dockerised container. The application can also be deployed locally on a user's own machine, most easily via R Studio, and can be hosted on any Shiny Hosting service including a self-hosting option. More details on hosting and the user cycle are provided in the report relating to deliverable 6.5 for the HIRMEOS Project.

The completed project was delivered and is available via the HIRMEOS Github repository at: https://github.com/hirmeos/shiny_dashboard

